

Study about effective factors on citizen's social trust in urban management (case study: Bonjar City)

Author's Details: Hamid Reza Shahidi Bonjar¹, Marzieh Miri², Hamid Okati³

¹MSc in Public Administration, University of Piame Noor, Tehran Branch, Tehran, Iran

²MSc in Geography and Urban Planning, Islamic Azad University of Zahedan, Zahedan, Iran (Corresponding Author)

³Academic staff of Islamic Azad University of Zabol, Zabol, Iran

Abstract

The main objective of this paper is to analyze the factors that can be effective in promoting citizen participation in urban development Bonjar and strategies to promote public participation in management decisions, investment participatory development approach to fulfill the offer. Methods of data collection based on a library of documents and field (questionnaire) and applied research - development and documentation methods, and analytical survey. Were using the SPSS. Excel statistical methods for data analysis have been used. Study area, the city is Bonjar in 2013. The population size of the household in 1022, according to the formula of Cochran's sample size was 350 households. Findings from this study based on one-sample t-test and Spearman is obtained. These demands pointed out the variables of social security, elections and participation in agricultural affairs, there is a significant connection between participation in municipal affairs. But household income variable is not significant connection with participation in municipal affairs. The results show the average theoretical assumptions about the number 3 are higher than the average paper. Note the t-test significance level of less than 0/05 (sig = 000) thus obtained can be generalized to the target population of the research theories are confirmed.

Keywords: Social Participation, Social Trust, Citizens, Urban Development, Bonjar City

Introduction:

If citizen participation in the co-ownership as a self-aware, then, citizens in work group to form and strengthen character traits such as leadership, responsibility tillage dealing with the ground for change in the stylized shall prepare and urban dynamics. Finally, the fact that participation was considered essential element in the sustainable development process, as it remembers that missing link in the development process. Experts will contribute to increase the competence and integrity of the people (Almond and et al, 1999: 42) citizen participation in decision making, planning and all the activities and affairs of the city, considered by managers, planners and expert's social development. Participatory process involving all groups of people in all stages of development, the emergence of the capacity, capability and consequently the growth and excellence of its material and spiritual. Perhaps for this reason, in recent years the scientific and political circles, the issue of citizen participation in urban affairs, community has been at the forefront of social and political conversation. Everyone as an important element in achieving sustainable development, democracy and drove words (Abbasazadah, 2009: 44). In this regard the city as the study area was selected Bonjar. The city enjoys its closeness to the

city Zabol, the potential for development. But unfortunately, due to lack of understanding of the potential, and the potential lack of proper prioritization of challenges on the city development planning process in the city has failed to lead the development of the city. Severe lack of coordination between levels of macro-and micro-management of intermediate and urban development, coordination in urban development plans (Complete Plans, Detailed Plans, Subject plans in other organizations, ...), urban management instability of financial resources, lack of fulfillment space per services that offer comprehensive design, unfair distribution utilities in urban areas and... Some of the challenges faced by urban managers in order to achieve urban development. Utilization of citizen participation in urban development planning, and dedication to their actual participation in, Can be a major influence to remove most of the problems and challenges of cities and urban development have access to. This research takes on to analyze the factors affecting participation in Bonjar achieving urban form and strengthen social participation is required.

Goals:

1- Measure the factors that influence citizen participation in urban development Bonjar.

2- Provide suggestions and strategies to promote increased citizen participation in urban development.

3- Promoting social cohesion and citizen engagement and trust using statistical analysis.

4- To motivate people to get involved in the decision making process and implementation.

Theory of Research:

1. Between social trust and citizen participation in municipal affairs, there is a significant connection.

2. Social connection and how citizens participate in the creation of economic and social influence in municipal affairs.

Method:

The present study sought to integrate contribute boundaries and urban development, in a way that results in Bonjar achieve. Such research wants, have the view the ability to have a holistic approach, as applied research - is developing. Method documentation, analysis and survey. For complete information, from sources such as the questionnaire is first class. The population studied included the questioning process is Bonjar citizens. Random sampling of the population. The sample size was estimated using the Cochran approach taken. According to the Population Bonjar (4080), people using Cochran's, about 350 questionnaires were required. The two models are used to describe and explain., Which describe and explain the plot Frequency distribution of means appropriate to assess the level and type of variables, hypothesis tests (one sample compare means tests, spearman correlation coefficient) was used 's.

The Background of research:

S.Dali (2004) in a study of social and cultural capital in the urban center of the London School of Economics has been discussed. This study focused on social participation by the Department of Culture

Media and Sport in the cultural sector is defined to build social capital.

Broger (2000) in an article entitled, necessary conditions for the development of regional infrastructure and low political importance of public participation in decision making and implementation are discussed., And cooperatives, and groups of Agriculture and the Self-help groups the goal of endogenous development will be emphasized.

Arash and Associated (2011) in a study using regression analysis of factors affecting women's participation in the preservation and revitalization, development and utilization of renewable natural resources from the perspective of natural resource experts have in Ilam province.

Abdi and Associated (2010) in a paper presented to the review guidelines to engage residents in the process of preparing and conducting informal areas of urban development have barriers to participation of the project relatively complete viewpoints discusses on the non-official reorganize settlement socio, appropriate framework to evaluate these theories. Expected, using effective tools for motivating participation, social development is the most basic terms, is unfortunately less, paving the way for the active participation of residents in improving their habitat returns.

A brief introduction of the study area:

City of Bonjar goes back to the early Qajar dynasty era. Bonjar city of Zabol city is one of the four points of the city center at a distance of 5 km east of the city (the city of Zabol) is located. The city center is Bonjar district. City Bonjar along an axis passing through the town center which plays a role in the joint communication with the city Zabol (West) and border town Doust Mohammad (East) is located. The West also hinder the development of a water channel is the physical side of Zabol Map No. 1 shows the geographical location of the study area.

Figure (1): The political situation in the region Bonjar, Source: Authors, 2013

Basics Theoretical of Research:

Social capital index is characterized by three main elements. In attitudes and behavioral intentions, trust and norms tend to teamwork and accountability, and participation in the community refers to the structural model. (Offe & fuche, 2002:157) David Driskell theorists on urban issues as well as the cities themselves better with the Kids believes that participation is based on the following three principles:

A: Development in the first place and above all to the benefit of local residents.

B: People who live in the planning area, most accurate information about the scope and topics related to it.

C: The people who most influenced the decision to accept a greater share of their participation in the decision-making process.

He participated in two more general forms of participation and non-participation are in place, with his disaffiliation forms of manipulation and fraud, and forms also include the participation of consulting social mobilization responsibility to involve the decisions (Driskell, 2002:32).

In today's society requires a high-level of human existence is felt and this coexistence is realized in the form of cities (Hakmatnia and Mousavi, 2008: 182) Chambers¹ (1995). Co-ownership approach that defines people's ability to make decisions, solve problems and selection methods, enables overcome local issues (Muraeedharan, 2008, 35). The

participation is a right, which reflects the role of individual members of the society together. Well as a social being, he is responsible for increased participation and led to legal delimitation is to achieve (Macdonald, 2000: 57). The participation is a requirement for participatory urban development planning and urban communities, improving the quality of urban communities and the tendency to spontaneous development of the society. Participation, meaning that is inherent in human societies need to strengthen the planning from the bottom up (Wangxiaojun, 2008, 86). In this paper, the main emphasis is on community participation in urban areas. And the objectives of oversight that voluntarily, knowingly, freely and actively and responsibly is one of the mechanisms of power.

Social trust:

Trust, as well as one of the dimensions of social capital impact on cooperation and interaction between groups and individuals will be. According to Putnam, social capital is a set of concepts of trust, norms and networks that contribute to improved communication and participation in the community, and finally will meet their mutual interests (Putnam, 2002: 322). Trust, social connection, and is a direct connection between social connection. So whatever social trust between individuals and social organizations, community groups and more for the same level of intensity of social communication, diversity is more stable (Kian Tajbakhsh, 2006:

210). According to Fukuyama, trust connection among members of the ruling family or tribe do not necessarily spread connection in society. What is the purpose of the trust, generalized trust is unknown. Typically, a high-level of trust among families in all communities what is causing fundamental differences between countries and regions, the level of generalized trust (Rahmani &

Amiri, 2008: 44)? Trust and cooperation also promotes collaboration among individuals, builds trust, trust is required to predict the behavior of an independent actor. Small community's intimate interlocking T prediction is done based on trust, the trust that is linked closely to the familiar, but in larger communities requires a more impersonal trust (Shady Talab & Hojati Karmani, 2009: 32).

The results describe the demographic characteristics

First theory: the connection between social trust of citizens and their participation in municipal affairs there.

An important group of decision makers in the length of stay:

Most of the respondents have stated that 76.6% of the length of stay in the city, important decisions is taken by the members. 14 percent believe that important decisions are taken by elders. 6% of people make educated decisions, and 4% of all the townspeople know the important decisions, they do share.

Table (1): An important group of decision makers in the length of stay

Yes		No		
Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	
6.0	18	94.0	281	Educated
14.0	42	86.0	257	Elders
76.6	229	23.4	70	Council
4.0	12	96.0	287	All the townspeople

Source: research results, 2013

The first shows to distribute items. That more than half of the respondents, 64.4 percent of them have stated that citizens can do some personal business to discuss with your friends. Most of the respondents to wit83.6 percent, with the statements that "when one of the families of the town is to travel to all the townspeople's trust and to anyone who has an interest in the care of their home leave" disagree completely disagree. 70.5% of respondents, most of the items "When a family is traveling to the city to take care of your home does not Nobody" and the opposition are quite the opposite. 73.7% of respondents, most of them have stated that they relied on their own citizens to solve problems. 86.2% of respondents with items' for all residents to help secure the city should "agree and totally agree. 93.7% of respondents believe that people take part in elections and councils.

Table (2): Distribution of items related to the first hypothesis

Totally disagree	Disagree	No comment	Agree	Totally agree	Question
1. 0%	10. 1%	24. 5%	57. 4%	7. 0%	Question 1
41. 8%	41. 8%	10. 4%	5. 1%	1. 0%	Question 2
9. 4%	61. 1%	21. 1%	5. 4%	3. 0%	Question 3
2. 3%	3. 0%	7. 0%	69. 3%	18. 3%	Question 4
1. 3%	8. 0%	17. 0%	57. 7%	16. 0%	Question 5
0. 7	4. 1	9. 2	63. 1	23. 1	Question 6
0. 3	1. 3	4. 7	36. 0	57. 7	Question 7

Source: research results, 2013

The connection between social security and participation in municipal affairs there:

To test the above theory test is used to compare the mean of one sample. Results of this test point out the mean of respondents' opinions (4.03) in conjunction with the effect of social security contributions in urban areas is higher than the theoretical mean the number 3. After considering the significance level of the test is lower than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), so the connection between these two variables is confirmed. Therefore, one can say with 95% confidence the level of social security has a positive effect on the level of citizen participation in municipal affairs.

Table (3): Evaluation of the relationship between social security and participation in municipal affairs

Test value: 3					
Significance level	Amount t-statistics	Standard error averages	Standard deviation	Averages	Number
0.001	1.593	0.02961	0.13715	4.0375	300

Source: research results, 2013

Connection between turnout and participation in municipal affairs there:

To find out this question, one-sample t test was used. The results of this study indicate the average citizen about the connection between turnout and participation in municipal affairs is equal to 4.49. The theoretical mean value (3) is much higher and it is a big difference. Given the significant level of the test is 0.000, so the connection between these two variables is significant. Therefore, one can say with 95% confidence the rate of participation in the elections, citizen participation in municipal affairs a positive impact.

Table (4): Evaluation of the relationship participation in elections and participation in municipal affairs

Test value: 3					
Significance level	Amount t-statistics	Standard error averages	Standard deviation	Averages	Number
0.000	3.701	0.02481	0.12041	4.4953	300

Source: research results, 2013

First theory: the connection between social trust of citizens and their participation in municipal affairs are:

To test the above theory test is used to compare the mean of one sample. Results of this test point out the mean of respondents' opinions (3.40) in conjunction with the effect of social trust and citizen participation in urban affairs from the theoretical mean the number 3 above. Considering the significance level of the test is less than 0.05 ($sig = 0.000$) is. Therefore, the results obtained can be generalized to the population and the researcher's

theory is confirmed. The higher the level of trust between the citizen participation in urban affairs and has more contrast with the decline of social trust, participation rates in urban affairs as well as reduced.

Table (5) The first hypothesis test

Test value: 3					
Significance level	Amount t-statistics	Standard error averages	Standard deviation	Averages	Number
0.000	10.834	0.14730	0.64801	3.4057	300

Source: research results, 2013

Survey questions related to the second theory

Second theory: the social connection of citizens will enhance their social and economic participation.

Distribution of items related to the second theory suggests the majority of respondents (77%) believe that their citizens pay tax. Nearly 40 percent of respondents believe the affairs of people involved in agriculture to help each other.

Table (6): Distribution of items related to the second hypothesis

Totally disagree	Disagree	No comment	Agree	Totally agree	Question
12.3	9.1	28.6	39.8	10.2	Question 1
1.0	4.7	17.3	68.3	8.7	Question 2

Source: research results, 2013

Between participation in agricultural affairs (dredging rill, farming and harvesting) and participation in municipal affairs, there are:

This question is for testing one sample test was used to compare the mean. Results of this test indicate the mean of respondents' opinions (3.265). In communication to the impact of agricultural affairs and their participation in urban affairs from the theoretical mean number 3 above. Considering the significance level of the test is less than 0.05 (sig = 0.001) is. The connection between the variables is confirmed. Therefore, with 95% confidence, we can say that participation in agricultural affairs (dredging rill, farming and harvesting) on effective participation in municipal affairs.

Table 7: Evaluation of participation in matters related to agriculture and urban participation rates in the affairs

Test value: 3					
Significance level	Amount t-statistics	Standard error averages	Standard deviation	Averages	Number
0.001	2.712	0.16184	0.55241	3.265	300

Source: research results, 2013

Household income:

Distribution of family income respondents indicate the majority 41.1% of their income was between five million Rials to 10 million Rials have income up 28.7 percent from 2500000 5000000 Rials IRR is 25.1% below the level of income of 2.5 million Rials and 5% of the respondents have higher income of 10 million Rials.

Table 8: Frequency distribution family income respondents

Percent valid	Percent	Frequency	
25.1	25.0	75	Less than the 2500000 Rials
28.8	28.7	86	From 2500000 to 5000000 Rials

41.1	41.0	123	five million Rials to 10 million Rials
5.0	5.0	15	have higher income of 10 million Rials
	3.	1	No Answer
	100.0	300	Total

Source: research results, 2013

Examine the connection between family income and level of participation in municipal affairs:

Based on the results of the Spearman test, test significance level higher than 0.05 (sig = 0.206) is. It can be said that the family income of the respondents and there was no significant connection between participation in municipal affairs. In other words, shared memory by increasing household income does not increase participation in municipal affairs.

Table (9): Evaluation of the relationship family income and level of participation in municipal affairs

Amounts	Statistics
0.073	Amount Spearman correlation coefficient
0.206	Significance level

Source: research results, 2013

The distribution of people's participation in building a mosque reveals that:

79.9% of the respondents have stated that most of the people involved in the construction of the mosque's economic participation, contributing 7.4 per cent of people think they participate, 11.4% believe that public participation in the construction of mosques, physical participation, and 3 percent said that none of the methods mentioned in mosque construction is not part of the public participation procedures.

Table (10): Frequency distribution of public participation in mosque construction

Yes		No		None
Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	
9	3.0	289	97.0	
22	7.4	276	92.6	Intellectual participation in mosque construction
238	79.9	60	20.1	Economic participation in mosque construction
34	11.4	264	88.6	Physical participation in mosque construction

Source: research results, 2013

Frequency distribution of public participation in school construction shows that:

Nearly half of the respondents, 42.5 percent said they had the kind of participation in the school building economic co-ownerships. 26.1% believe the people involved in making the school are physically involved. 20.1% of people thought in terms of building schools take part. And 12.4 percent among any of the methods mentioned methods do not account for people's participation in school construction.

Table 11: Frequency distribution of people's participation in school construction

Yes		No		None
Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	
12.4	37	87.6	262	
20.1	60	79.9	239	Intellectual participation in School

				construction
42.5	127	57.5	172	Economic participation in School construction
26.1	78	73.9	221	Physical participation in School construction

Source: research results, 2013

Frequency distribution of respondents' opinions with regard to public participation in the construction of roads and road shows that:

Nearly half of the respondents to wit 41.1 percent have stated the type of participation in the construction of roads and highways, economic participation is 23.1 percent of the participation of the people involved think they know, the 12% of people physically making the road or through co-ownership would be 23.7 percent believe that any of the methods listed among the methods of public participation in the construction of roads and highways is not.

Table (12): Frequency distribution of public participation in the construction of roads

Yes		No		
Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	
23.7	71	76.3	228	None
23.1	69	76.9	230	Intellectual participation in Road construction
41.1	123	58.9	176	Economic participation in Road construction
12.0	36	88.0	263	Physical participation in Road construction

Source: research results, 2013

Second theory: the social communication of citizens will enhance their social and economic participation.

To test the above theory test is used to compare the mean of one sample. The results of this test indicate that the mean of respondents' opinions regarding the effect of enhancing the participation of citizens in their social communication is 3.11. The number 3 is higher than the theoretical mean. And according to the t-test significance level of less than 0.05 (sig = 0.000) is therefore the result is extended to the population. This suggests the theory is confirmed by the investigator. Means to enhance citizen participation, social and economic ties to their will.

Table (13): The second hypothesis test

Test value: 3					
Significance level	Amount t-statistics	Standard error averages	Standard deviation	Averages	Number
0.000	3.682	0.33030	0.13525	3.1117	300

Source: research results, 2013

Conclusions:

Town planning, urban development requires attention to the processes that are created in different aspects of citizens' activities and directing the process of urban development requires the active and informed participation of key stakeholders in the management of urban development. After surveying the field of scientific study and research in Bonjar following results are obtained. To survey the connection between the level of social security, participation in agricultural affairs, and participation in municipal elections with the participation of one-sample t test was used. The results of this study point out that each of these factors have a positive effect on participation in municipal affairs. And the connection between participation in municipal affairs is significant. Participation in elections among these variables (4.490) may have the greatest impact.

To test the first hypothesis test is used to compare the mean of one sample. And given the significant level of the test is less than 0.05 (sig = 0.000) is. Therefore, the results obtained can be generalized to the population

and the researcher's theory is confirmed. The confidence of the citizen is higher, the greater the degree of their participation in municipal affairs. And reverse the decline in social trust, participation rate in urban areas is also reduced. Based on the results of the Spearman test, test significance level higher than 0.05 (sig = 0.206) is. Therefore be said the family income of the respondents and there was no significant connection between participation in municipal affairs. Based on the frequency distribution of public participation in making (mosques, schools, roads and paths) shows most of the respondents have stated the type of public participation, economic participation. To test the second theory test is used to compare the mean of one sample. Given the t-test significance level of less than 0.05 (sig = 0.000), so it can be said the results obtained are applicable to the target population. As well as the researcher's theory is confirmed. The social communication of citizens will strengthen their social and economic participation.

Suggestions

- ❖ strengthen and upgrade the legal status of the City Council of the Municipality Council, the Council for institutions and organizations of all groups
- ❖ The use of audio-visual media, newspapers and ... To increase public awareness and urban managers
- ❖ belief and commitment to urban managers value the views of citizens
- ❖ build trust between citizens and urban management
- ❖ opinions of citizens on city projects and programs
- ❖ Creating exhibitions focusing on citizen participation.
- ❖ Cooperating with the city management education for the development of cultural activities on citizen participation.

Reference:

- Abbaszadah, M, (2009), Examined the factors that influence citizen participation in the affairs (case study the city of Isfahan) Supervisor, R.Rabani & V. Ghasemi, a sociology PHD thesis, University of Isfahan.
- Abdi, B, Soltani, A, Bazrgar, M.R, Amjadi, J, (2010), Strategies for informal settlement resident's participation (in the process of developing and carrying out urban development projects, identified in the spring and summer
- Almond and et al, (2002), Comparative Politics, translated by A. Tayeb, Tehran: Center and Public Administration.
- Araiash, B, Houssaini, F, (2011), A regression analysis of factors affecting women's participation in the preservation, restoration, development and utilization of renewable natural resources from the perspective of natural resource experts Ilam province, Journal of Agricultural Sciences and Technology, No. 1 .
- Azkiya, M & Ghafari, G.R, (2003), Rural development with emphasis on the rural community of Iran, Tehran, Nashre Ney Publications.
- claus and fuchs,Susanne, (2002), A decline social capital The German case,published in Putnam, Robert D(2002)Democracy in flux: The Evolution of social capital in contemporary society.New York: oxford university press.
- Daly, Siobhan. (2004) social capital and the cultural sector centre for civil society , London school of Economics
- Driskell, David, (2002), creating Better cities with children and youth,A manual for participation, London and Newyork.
- Hakamtania, H & Mousavi, M, (2008), Evaluation of factors influencing the satisfaction of the citizens of the municipality, case study the city of Yazd, Journal of Geography and Development, University of Zahedan, No. 9.
- Khalagh Abadi, S.A, (1998), (Effect of participation. . .) Rural Development, No. 5 and 6, the Center for Rural Studies, Tehran.
- Macdonald, Laura,(2000), citizen ship participation the public sphere in the Americans university
- Mohseni Tabrizi, A, (1990), Evaluation of rural areas and its connection to participatory agricultural extension, Jihad-e-Construction, Deputy promoting public participation, Iran's Plan of Compilation Promotion System.
- Muraleedharan. K, (2008) Dynamics of people participation in development: A study with special reference to women participation in the local level planning in Kerala, Eldis Participation Resource Guide.
- Piran, P, (1995), Schools-Mayor towards institutionalization of social participation, Deputy of social and cultural, Office of Social Research of Tehran.
- Putnam, R, (2002), Democracy and civil traditions, translated by, M.T.Dalfrouz, Ministry of Interior, Department of Political Studies.

- Rahmani, T, Amiri, M, (2008), Examines the impact on economic growth in the belief in Iranian provinces using spatial econometrics, Economic Studies, No. 78
- Schubler, peter, (1996), participation and partner ship in urban management and in frastrueture. washington D.C: programme by word bank
- Shady Talab, Zh & Hojati Karmani, F, (2009), Poverty and social capital in rural communities, Journal of social welfare, Year VIII, No. 28.
- Tajbakhsh, K, (2006), Social capital (trust, democracy and development), Translated by, Afshin Khakbaz & Hassan Pouian, Tehran Nashre Shiraze Publications.
- Wang, xiaojun and zhenrongyu, (2008), stave ginderdy, johnforrester, vol.28, april.